

**The Potential Role of Cooperatives in Creating
Employment opportunities in the
Sudan A case Study of Khartoum State**

By

DR ISLAH HASSAN ELAWAD

**University of Northern Border, Faculty of Business
Management, Department of Human Resources
Management**

Sudia Arabia

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate and analyse the problem of youth unemployment in the Sudan and to explore the potential role of cooperatives in creating employment opportunities for youth, as well as its impact in the socio- economic benefits. Cooperatives has been identified as one of the tools which act as an incubator for small enterprises and provide credit collateral for its members.

Youth unemployment became an alarming phenomenon worldwide statistic shows that the youth are estimated to be about 1.8 billion, of the world's population (Population Reference Bureau, 2013) which attract the researcher concern and policy makers particularly in developing countries. The recent statistics of International Labor Organization (ILO) indicates that youth unemployment in the Sudan accounting for about 24.5% in 2013, which is higher than the average rate of African countries and the Arab Region. The same statistics also reveals that the rate of unemployment among female youth is very high compared to male counterparts, with the percentage of 27.5 and 22.6 for female and male, respectively.

In The Sudan the informal sector absorbed the bulk of the labor force of both sexes particularly in the urban areas where the migrants and displaced concentrated. The informal sector is characterized by easy access and a variety of job opportunities which needs no high skills such as food making and services. This situation generally reflects the reality of unemployment status and indicates the importance of narrowing this gab.

The study falls into four chapters. Chapter one is an introductory chapter consists of background to the study, it proceeded to describe the significant of the study, together with some concepts that related to the topic specifically cooperatives concepts and its implications in the socio-economic process.

The main aim of this study is to: 1. To identify the challenges, legal framework, and the needs to promote youth employment through cooperatives in Sudan particularly Khartoum State. 2. Identify the institutional and management needs for successfully starting and running cooperatives by young males and females in the rural and urban areas. 3. To identify areas where there is no policy at all, and to examine the absence of relevant policies on the promotion cooperatives. 4. To identify policies, measures and priority actions to accelerate the process of enhancing youth employment and the participation of youth in the economy. 5. To advocate

the creation of informal lending units administered by the youth to help create self-employment through cooperatives associations.

The study is based on the following hypotheses: 1. Cooperative societies can combat unemployment among graduates. 2. - Cooperative societies can provide collective financing for their members (women and men) for self-employment. 3. - Cooperative societies can provide bank guarantees or collateral to their members to run their small enterprises.

Chapter two about the literature review and theoretical framework views and approaches about cooperatives to reflect the extent of the effective role of cooperatives and its implications in society. Within the context of the politico-socio-economic development of the Sudan. It is composed of three sections, section (1) aimed to review some of the relevant literature on youth unemployment, its definitions, concepts, measures and influences. Section (2) aimed to review the available literature about cooperatives concepts, definitions dimensions, and roles implications. Section (3) is set out to shed lights on the historical background and evolution of cooperative movement in the Sudan. Chapter three is about Cooperatives and Equity support as Components of Self Employment it is consisted of a review about cooperatives and credits unions, as the most important and successful financial institutions and self-employment mechanism. It is also proceeded to review the aspects of credits associations in the Sudan, and the result of the questionnaire. Chapter Four is a summary , results and recommendations of the study.

Summary, Results and Recommendations

4.1. Summary: -

The issue of unemployment among youth has gained a considerable attention over the globe young people (population ages between 15 and 24) have fewer opportunities to participate in labor markets compared to the active adult population. Recent statistics show that young people in the world are estimated to be about 1.8 billion, representing one quarter of the world's population (Population Reference Bureau, 2013). More than 70 million of them are unemployed with drastic economic and social conditions. In addition, most employed youth workers engage in hazardous jobs and informal sector, and their transition to decent work is slow and difficult (ILO, 2013).

Sudan has witnessed development crises, internal conflicts, ethnic strife, war and socio-political and economic disasters that collaboratively impede transparency and equity in the allocation of national resources. As regards human resources development, it is worth mentioning that the impact of macro-economic policies in human development has both negative and positive bearings on human resources development agenda and infrastructure. The existence of unemployment pockets differs from one State to the other, and directly affects both rural communities and urban centers.

4.2. Results: -

The findings of the questionnaire conducted for the purposes of this study show that 54.2 %. cooperatives help generate employment opportunities. This reflects that the majority of unemployed youth respondents prefer self-employment. As 62% of cooperatives provide Microfinance. In the Sudan access to credit allows poor people to take the advantage of economic opportunities. While increased earnings are by no means automatic. It is evident that clients who join a cooperative and obtain micro credits have better economic conditions and have also shown that over a long period of time many clients do come out of unemployment.

While 12.0%. of cooperatives are in the services sector. 58.3 %. Of cooperatives help ensure food security. that 81.3 %. of cooperatives help in reducing poverty. 75.0% indicates that cooperatives promote rural small enterprises. 77.1% of cooperatives promote socioeconomic development by increasing family income and improve family wellbeing.

4.3. Recommendations: -

Relying on the above the following recommendations could be suggested: -

4.3.1. In the area of Youth Employment: -

- Matching between the education outcome and the labor market demand should be considered.
- Reenforce and enhance the various initiatives pertaining to youth employment to reduce unemployment among both sexes.
- Work in the informal sector should be recognized as active work which constitutes to development.
- Young people should be provided with formal and informal training and professional training to enhance their access to employment and thereby improve their social well-being.

4.3.2. Recommendations in the area of cooperatives:-

The central recommendations in the area of cooperatives are as follows:
In order to expand cooperatives sector and concept the study raise the following recommendations we need to adopt and emphasize cooperatives strategy that focuses on the following goals: -

- (1) Development of strategies that improve the sector based on the cooperatives values.
- (2) Development of specific policy to govern the sector and integrate it in the strategic plans of the country.
- (3) Mainstreaming cooperative culture and identification of the self-employment strategies that can take the youth into a level of socio- economic wellbeing hence increase their autonomy.
- (4) Emphasis on capacity building management, business skills training and transparent, democratic structures are intended to ensure sound management and institutional sustainability.

To conclude we can ascertain the fact that cooperative model offers new opportunities to involve communities and individuals in socio - economic development process. And can facilitate smallholder farmers'

youth and the needy segment in the society linkages to export markets and have the full potential to strengthen livelihood.

مستخلص الدراسة باللغة العربية

تهدف هذه الدراسة الى تقصى وتحليل مشكلة البطالة وسط الشباب في السودان واستكشاف الدور المحتمل للجمعيات التعاونية في توليد فرص الاستخدام لأعضائها. وأيضا لاستكشاف دورها في تحقيق الفوائد الاقتصادية والاجتماعية. تمثل الجمعيات التعاونية احدى الأدوات او الحاضنات للمشروعات الصغيرة، كما وتعمل على توفير ضمانات القروض البنكية لأعضائها. أضحت بطالة الشباب ظاهرة عالمية حيث تشير الإحصاءات الى ان الشباب يمثلون حوالي 1.8 بليون من سكان العالم التي لفتت اهتمما الباحثين وصانعي السياسات خاصة في الدول النامية.

تشير الإحصاءات الحديثة لمنظمة العمل الدولية الى ان بطالة الشباب في السودان تمثل 24.5% في العام 2013 حيث تعتبر الأعلى على مستوى الدول الافريقية. تمثل الجمعيات التعاونية أدوات وحاضنات للمشروعات الصغيرة كما وتعمل على توفير ضمان القروض لأعضائها.

أضحت بطالة الشباب ظاهرة عالمية حيث تشير الإحصاءات الى ان الشباب يمثلون حوالي 1.8 بليون من سكان العالم. الامر الذي لفت اهتمام الباحثين وصانعي السياسات خاصة في الدول النامية.

تشير الاحصاءات الحالية لمنظمة العمل الدولية الى ان بطالة الشباب في السودان تمثل حوالي 24.5% في العام 2013 حيث تعتبر الأعلى على مستوى الدول الافريقية والعربية. تشير نفس الإحصاءات أيضا الى ان نسبة البطالة وسط الاناث عالية مقارنة مع رصفائهم الذكور بنسبة 27.5 و22.6 للإناث والذكور تراتبيا.

في السنوات الأخيرة بذلت الحكومة جهود عديدة لمكافحة مشكلة البطالة تضمنت انشاء الوزارة الاتحادية والولاية للشباب والرياضة. كما وشدت استراتيجيات اتحادية وولائية (2007-2013) كما وتم انشاء صندوق لتشغيل الخريجين بولاية الخرطوم والولايات الأخرى.

في السودان يستوعب القطاع غير الرسمي اغلبية القوى العاملة من الجنسين خاصة في المناطق الحضرية حيث يتمركز المهاجرين والنازحين ويتميز القطاع غير الرسمي بسهولة الدخول وتنوع فرص الاستخدام التي لا تحتاج الى مهارات عالية مثل قطاع الخدمات وبيع الأطعمة. هذا الوضع يعكس حقيقة وضع الاستخدام ويوضح أهمية ضرورة العمل على ردم هذه الفجوة.

توفر التعاونيات مئات ملايين الوظائف وتستوعب أكثر من مليون عضو (ماتا 2013) انتشار ظاهرة البطالة اثرت على العائلات في الدول النامية والسودان ليس استثناء.

تقع الدراسة في أربعة فصول الفصل الأول عبارة عن مقدمة تشتمل على خلفية للدراسة، كما يصف أهمية الدراسة والمفاهيم ذات الصلة بموضوعها بتركيز على مفهوم التعاونيات وانعكاساته في عملية التنمية الاجتماعية والاقتصادية.

الهدف الأساسي من هذه الدراسة هو: -

1- تعريف التحديات والإطار التشريعي والحاجة لتطوير تشغيل الشباب من خلال التعاونيات في السودان والفقراء خاصة النساء عائلات الاسر.

2- تحديد المؤسسة والإدارة التي يحتاجها الشباب من الجنسين لإدارة التعاونيات.

3- تحديد المجالات التي لا توجد بها سياسات لتطوير التعاونيات.

4- تحديد السياسات والمعايير واولويات العمل لتطوير وتسريع تشغيل الشباب.

5- مناصرة تأسيس وحدات التمويل غير الرسمي بواسطة الشباب لتساعد في الاستخدام عبر الجمعيات التعاونية.

استندت الدراسة على الفرضيات التالية: -

1- يمكن للجمعيات التعاونية مكافحة البطالة وسط الشباب.

2- يمكن للجمعيات التعاونية ان توفر التمويل الجماعي لأعضائها.

3- يمكن الجمعيات التعاونية ان توفر الضمانات للبنوك لمساعدة أعضائها من ممارسة أعمالهم الصغيرة.

الفصل الثاني تناول الإطار النظري للدراسة وعرض الأدبيات والاتجاهات في مجال التعاونيات ويعكس مدى فعالية دور التعاونيات في المجتمع. يتضمن الفصل الثاني ثلاث أقسام، القسم رقم (1) يهدف الى مراجعة الأدبيات في مجال بطالة الشباب، تعريفها، ومفاهيمها وأثرها. القسم رقم (2) يهدف الى مراجعة الأدبيات المتوفرة عن التعاونيات وتعريفها وابعادها ودورها في التنمية الاجتماعية والاقتصادية. القسم رقم (3) يلقي الضوء على الخلفية التاريخية وتطور الحركة التعاونية في السودان.

الفصل الثالث عن التعاونيات كآليات ومكون للعدالة والاستخدام الذاتي وكمؤسسات مالية فعالة. الفصل الرابع يعرض الخلاصة ونتائج الدراسة والتوصيات.

توصلت الدراسة الى النتائج الآتية: -

1- أظهرت نتائج الاستبيان الذي اعد لأغراض هذه الدراسة ان التعاونيات يمكنها توليد فرص التشغيل الذاتي بنسبة 54.2% وان 62% من التعاونيات توفر التمويل الأصغر لعضويتها.

2- في السودان الوصول للتمويل يمكن الباحثين عن العمل من الشباب من استغلال إيجابيات الفرص الاقتصادية بينما تعتبر زيادة الدخل تلقائية. الشاهد ان الذين انضموا للجمعيات التعاونية او حصلوا على قروض صغيرة نجد أوضاعهم قد تحسنت وتجاوزا مرحلة البطالة.

3- بتقليل الانكشاف وزيادة الدخل تمكن أعضاء الجمعيات التعاونية من توفير احتياجاتهم المعيشية، وقد أكدت نتائج الاستبيان ان التعاونيات ساعدت بتوليد فرص الاستخدام بنسبة 54.2% حيث تعمل التعاونيات في مجال الخدمات بنسبة 12% وساهمت في توفير الامن الغذائي بنسبة 58.3%. وساهمت بنسبة 75% في تطوير الصناعات الريفية الصغيرة و77% في التنمية الاقتصادية والاجتماعية.

استنادا على النتائج اعلاه يمكن اقتراح التوصيات التالية: -

2-1- توصيات في مجال بطالة الشباب: -

- يجب الاهتمام بموانمة مخرجات التعليم لمتطلبات سوق العمل.
- تعزيز ودعم كل المبادرات المتعلقة بتشغيل الشباب لتقليل البطالة وسم الشباب.
- ضرورة الاعتراف واعلاء قيمة العمل في القطاع غير الرسمي كعمل يصب في الناتج القومي الإجمالي.
- تزويد الشباب بالتدريب الرسمي وغير الرسمي والمهني والحرفي لتعزيز دخول الشباب للتشغيل وتحسين مستواهم الاجتماعي.

2-2- التوصيات في مجال التعاونيات: -

- 1- تطوير استراتيجيات لتحسين قطاع التعاون تستند على قيم التعاون.
- 2- تطوير سياسات محددة تحكم القطاع وادماجها في الاستراتيجية والخطط القومية.
- 3- نشر ثقافة التعاون وتعريف استراتيجيات الاستخدام الذاتي التي تحسن الأوضاع الاجتماعية والاقتصادية للشباب.
- 4- التأكيد على بناء القدرات والتدريب وصقل المهارات للأعمال الصغيرة والاستدامة المؤسسية.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

PESTEL:	Political	Economic	Social	Technological	Law.
ILO:	International		Labor		Organization
ICA:	International	Exchange.:		Women	And
	Development.				

MDGs: Millennium Development Goals.

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

USAID: United States Agency for International Development.

NGO's: None Governmental Organizations.

SDF: Social Development Foundation.

UNDP: United Nations Development Programs.

CBOs: Community Based Organizations.

S D A: Social Development Associations

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1. Introduction: -

According to Jurger S. (1997), cooperatives are successful in fostering economic development because they are for-profit businesses that uphold principles other than those connected to the exclusive pursuit of profit. In addition to being companies first and foremost, cooperatives also uphold economic justice by guaranteeing equal access to markets and services for all of its open, voluntary membership base. Cooperatives typically make decisions that strike a balance between the need for profitability and the larger interests of the community they serve since they are owned by the customers who use their services.

Cooperatives do have a comparative job creation advantage over other types of enterprises: they are labor intensive by nature, they are cost-effective because of member commitment and participation, they generate economies of scale and scope through horizontal and vertical integration, they establish links between the informal and the formal sectors, and they put economic and social development on a broader base. Worker-owned cooperatives provide their members with decent, permanent jobs while client-owned cooperatives which are predominant in the agricultural sector, can stabilize existing self-employment in rural areas; financial cooperatives can mobilize savings among the poorest and thus accumulate capital for productive investment; and social cooperatives provide self-employed workers with a minimum of social security and creating jobs in the social service sector.

Bookman et al (1984) proposes three-pronged strategy to exploit the employment creation potential of cooperatives fully as: (I) Support to Macro Reforms and to Capacity Building in Organizations, That Provide Assistance to Cooperatives: Policy, legal and institutional reforms are still necessary in some countries to create a favourable climate for cooperative development. The design and implementation of such reforms usually require highly

specialized, short-term expertise that development partners should make available. Secondly, many agencies, including NGOs, promote cooperatives and similar associations without having the appropriate expertise. Follow-up programs to cooperative reforms should therefore include capacity-building at this level “cooperative enterprises provide the organizational means whereby a significant proportion of humanity is able to take into its own the tasks of creating productive employment, overcoming poverty and achieving social integration”. The present research will demonstrate that cooperatives can effectively create and maintain self-employment in both the rural and urban areas.

Cooperative enterprises provide the organizational means whereby a significant proportion of humanity can take into its own the tasks of creating productive employment, overcoming poverty and achieving social integration". The present research will demonstrate that cooperatives can effectively create and maintain self-employment in both the rural and urban in the Sudan particularly Khartoum State where the bulk of the population lives in its rural area.

2. Statement of the Research Problem:-

A cooperative is an autonomous association of women and men, who unite voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise (Levin, 2003). It is a business enterprise that seeks to strike a balance between pursuing profit and meeting the needs and interests of members and their communities. Cooperatives not only provide members with economic opportunities, but also offer them a wide range of services and opportunities.

The cooperative enterprise model exists in many sectors, including agriculture, consumer issues, marketing and financial services, and housing.

1.3. Research Significance: -

Cooperatives are effective instruments for socio-economic development and provide modes of living, particularly under the liberalization of the economy and the changing role of the States particularly in developing world. Cooperatives were invented to enable people to adjust their way of living and working requirements of the market economy, in order to survive as small actors in a world dominated by capital, markets and competition.

1.4. Objectives of the study:

2. To identify the challenges, legal framework, and the needs to promote youth employment through cooperatives in Sudan as well as the poor particularly women headed households.
 3. Identify the institutional and management needs for successfully starting and running cooperatives by young males and females in the rural and urban areas.
 4. To identify areas where there is no policy at all, and to examine the absence of relevant policies on the promotion cooperatives.
 5. To identify policies, measures and priority actions to accelerate the process of enhancing youth employment and the participation of youth in the economy.
- 5.To advocate the creation of informal lending units administered by the youth to help create self-employment through cooperatives associations.

1.5. Research Hypotheses: -

- 1- Cooperative societies can combat unemployment among graduates.
- 2- Cooperative societies can provide collective financing for their members (women and men) for self-employment.
- 3- Cooperative societies can provide bank guarantees or collateral to their members to run their small enterprises.

2.5 Scope of the Research: -

Cooper and Schindler (2008) view the scope as the breadth and depth of a topic's coverage (by time frame, geography, criteria for inclusion etc). In the proposed study, the scope is reviewed in terms of the subject, area and time. In terms of subject, it is limited to the discipline of socio-economic development, (employment creation) With respect to geographical (area) scope, the proposed study was conducted in the Republic of Sudan when the country witnessed the growing of massive unemployment among graduates, and none graduates.

3.5 Methodology of the Research: - The research will adopt the qualitative method which based on non-numerical data as well as quantitative methods focusing on cooperative movement and its implications in development process in the Sudan.

1.6. Methods of data collection: -

Social scientists use three main methods for collecting data: These are: (1) observation, (2) The use of existing data, and (3) asking questions. Relying on this the researcher decided that the three techniques are going to be used for the following reasons:

- (1) Observation is superior to other methods of data collection as it describes the certain features of past situations the use of observation allows the researcher to describe what actually happens in reality.
 - (2) Use of existing secondary source material.
 - (3) The interview, as it used in most developing countries is a prominent technique in collecting data.
- 4) PESTEL analysis, used as an analytical tool which considers external factors and helps the planners and policy makers to think about their impacts.

Chapter Two

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

The aim of this chapter is to review some of the basic conceptual theoretical framework, views and approaches about cooperatives to reflect the extent of the effective role of cooperatives and its implications in society.

Views, that are expressed to provide a framework for this study, were considered within the context of the politico-socio-economic development of the Sudan. Bearing in mind the incorporation of capitalist relations in the social formation of the world economy, the penetration of the capitalist relations in the social formation of the Sudanese society, has affected both women and men. The spread of unemployment phenomenon has thus come to affect the households in the developing countries of which Sudan is no exemption. However, the subordination and marginalization of the poor is not only economically based, but it has also been enhanced by various socio-economic and political factors resulting in the reproduction of the system as a whole.

This chapter is composed of three sections, section (1) aimed to review some of the relevant literature on unemployment, its definitions, concepts, measures and influences. Section (2) aimed to review the available literature about cooperatives concepts, definitions dimensions, and roles implications. Section (3) is set out to shed lights on the historical background and evolution of cooperative movement in the Sudan.

Section one

2.1.1. Introduction: -

This section is set -out to review some of the basic conceptual framework, views, and approaches about unemployment such as unemployment definitions, measures, trends in unemployment over time its dimensions, understanding of unemployment, unemployment reduction strategies, unemployment and development, human capital and the effects of unemployment, safety nets, and social policy.

Cooperatives play a significant role in many national economies and have created a great number of salaried jobs and self- employment opportunities in Africa of which Sudan is no exception. Yet the role of cooperatives in employment creation has been neglected by employment planners, cooperative promotion agencies, social partners and donor organizations alike. In many African countries, cooperatives were considered primarily as tools to execute certain economic or political functions on behalf of the government, not as autonomous, members-based organizations that create and consolidate self-employment. This policy of "incorporation" has done great damage to cooperative development in Sudan. Fortunately, government policies towards cooperatives have changed after economic reforms and democratization process that have taken place. Today the economic political legal and administrative environment of many nations is conducive to the development of genuine, self- reliant and autonomous cooperatives and similar organizations which can greatly contribute to job creation and to the empowerment of the poorest and unemployment graduates. This opportunity must be seized. Studies shows that cooperatives have created a sizeable number of salaried jobs; yet, their biggest employment creation potential lies in the field of direct and indirect self-employment Bailey (1992).

Compared to other business models, cooperatives do have a comparative advantage in creating jobs because they are labor-intensive by nature, cost-effective due to member commitment and

participation, and they create economies of scale and scope through horizontal and vertical integration. Additionally, they forge connections between the informal and formal sectors and broaden the foundation for social and economic development. Financial cooperatives can mobilize savings among the poorest and accumulate capital for productive investment; worker-owned cooperatives offer their members decent, permanent jobs; client-owned cooperatives, which are primarily in the agricultural sector, can stabilize existing self-employment in rural areas; and social cooperatives, which create jobs in the social service sector and offer a minimum level of social security to self-employed workers.

Bookman et al (1984) proposes three-pronged strategy to exploit the employment creation potential of cooperatives fully as: -

- (I) Support to Macro Reforms and capacity building in organization that aid cooperatives: Policy, legal and institutional reforms are still necessary in some countries to create a favorable climate for cooperative development. The design and implementation of such reforms require highly specialized, short-term expertise that development partners should make available. Secondly, many agencies, including NGOs, promote cooperatives and similar associations without having the appropriate expertise. Follow-up programs to cooperative reforms should therefore include capacity-building at this level.
- (II) Promotion of worker -owned cooperatives, social cooperatives and financial cooperatives, which have received very little support until now, have a high potential to create additional employment in industry, transport, services and other sectors with relatively small investment; they can also participate in the privatization of public enterprises through workers takeovers. Worker-owned cooperatives can be successful when they have access to appropriate

technical assistance and financial institutions. Social cooperatives.

(111). The Employment Creation Potential of Cooperatives: -

It is important to underline that most cooperatives are not instrument of employment promotion but enterprises that give their members economic activities. This notwithstanding, “cooperative enterprises provide the organizational means whereby a significant proportion of humanity is able to take into its own the tasks of creating to take into its own the tasks of creating productive employment, overcoming poverty and achieving social integration”.

2-1-2-DEFINITIONS AND CONCEPTS OF UNEMPLOYMENT: -

The term unemployment refers to a situation where a person actively searches for employment but is unable to find work.

A person is said to be unemployed when he or she is able and willing to work and is available for work (that is, the person is actively searching for employment) but does not find work. The number of people unemployed in an economy is the number of people whom that description fits.

On the other hand a low unemployment rate, means that the economy is more likely to be producing near its full capacity, maximizing output, driving wage growth, and raising living standards over time.

Types of Unemployment: -

Economists divide unemployment into many different categories. The two broadest categories are voluntary and involuntary unemployment. When unemployment is voluntary, it means that a person left their job willingly in search of other employment. When it is involuntary, it means that a person was fired or laid off and must now look for another job.

According to U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. "Concepts and Definitions (CPS)". Voluntary and involuntary unemployment can be broken down into four types. As stated below: -

-Frictional Unemployment: -

Results from the normal turnover of labor. An important source of frictional unemployment is young people who enter the labor force and look for jobs. Another source is people who are in the process of changing their jobs and are caught between one job and the next.

Structural Unemployment: -

Refers to unemployment arising because there is mismatch of skills and job opportunities when the pattern of demand and production changes.

Demand-Deficit Unemployment: -

This refers to Keynesian unemployment, when aggregate demand falls and wages and prices have not yet adjusted to restore full employment.

Classical Unemployment: -

Describes the unemployment created when the wage is deliberately maintained above the level at which the labour supply and labour demand schedules intersect.

Institutional Unemployment: -

Institutional unemployment results from long-term or permanent institutional factors and incentives in the economy.

What Are the Main Causes of Unemployment?

- There are many reasons for unemployment. These include recessions, depressions, technological improvements, job outsourcing, and voluntarily leaving one job to find another.

Section Two

2.2.1. Introduction: -

This section aimed to review the available literature about cooperatives concepts, definitions dimensions, and roles implications. As well as exploring the roots of cooperatives movement globally. It is set out to shed light on the extent of the potential role of cooperatives, in development as a survival model to job creation and as a tool to unite local communities particularly in developing countries. ILO and ICA (2014) argue about the role of the cooperatives to contribute to poverty reduction, sustainable development, empowering women, and to realize equality between members regardless sex; race; religion; and ethnicity. Smith and Rath Baum (2013) contend that cooperatives have contributed to job creation in the recent financial crisis and other periods of economic turmoil, and they have comparative advantages in generating innovation as cooperatives in the agricultural sector have had an important and well documented history of innovation.

Birchall (2004) discusses the role of cooperatives in the context of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). He argues cooperatives come in several forms including consumer, housing, agricultural cooperatives, and worker cooperatives that provide decent work to their members. He recognizes cooperatives' potential as organizations of the poor and has a substantial record over many years in lifting whole groups of people out of poverty in the now developed world. He refers to the disappointing experiences of cooperatives in developing countries and provides some suggestions to enhance their role in the development process.

Curt (2010) explains that cooperatives can provide a dignified living for the many millions who would have otherwise been unemployed and the author ascertain this as fact particularly for graduates employment, or marginalized groups. He adds, people

band together into cooperatives because they need others to shape work experience and expertise.

Considering the role of the cooperatives to empower marginalized groups of people, Mendoza (2013) discusses the role of cooperatives to empower indigenous people. He argues that the indigenous people who count 5 % of the world population and found across the world. They have faced historic injustice resulting from racism, discrimination, and inequalities long suffered by these people around the world. He adds, they are widely found in the poverty trap and vulnerability as they count about 15% of the world's poor, as being a woman; indigenous or afro descendant; or landless is enough to multiply their vulnerability. This ascertain the essential role of Cooperatives in the society and its benefit to all segments in the society regard less of sex as a social mechanism that provide inclusion and services to the people in the local community.

The co-operative values are based on the values of self-help, self-responsibility, democracy, equality, equity and solidarity.

Cooperatives came into existence in western Europe and in parts of the U.S.A. and Australia in the seventeenth century to allow small producers to assert their independence more effectively and these cooperatives contribute significantly to succession from subsistence to market economy. Between 1914 and 1950, five categories of cooperatives were observed: the consumer cooperative pioneered by Rochdale of England, worker cooperatives in France, credit cooperative in Germany, the agricultural cooperative in Denmark, Germany and housing cooperative emerged in parts of the industrialized Europe (Mango 2013).

The perception of cooperatives in Europe and USA was underpinned by the ideology economic growth. While in Africa it was influenced by colonialism whose masters wanted to increase food production for their industrial workers (delevtre.2008).

Research projects of ILO on the contribution of cooperatives to employment have elaborated on the variety of ways in which marketing cooperatives, client owned cooperatives, credit cooperatives, consumer cooperatives and worker owned cooperatives have impacted positively on employment and income, more specifically cooperatives can make specific contribution to employment generation through worker-ownership.

Section Three

Historical Background of Cooperative Movement in the Sudan

1-3- Introduction: -

This section is set out to high light on the extent and evolution of cooperatives movement in the Sudan as well as its status.

In the East Sudan region (Baraka) in the Delta Tokar, the British authorities made the initial attempts to create primary cooperatives in 1921. Because they were surrounded by pastoralists rather than permanent farmers, the experiment itself failed, and the farmers then failed to repay the funding.

In the latter part of the 1930s, a second experiment known as cooperative partnerships (quasicooperatives) was conducted in the Northern district at Hafeer Mashhour area in 1937. The experiment's foundation was the villager participation, wherein the villagers pooled their savings in order to purchase a water pump for the purpose of irrigating the lands of two or more neighboring villages.

The first cooperatives law was enacted in 1948, which combined the functions of the cooperative societies' registrar with that of the director of the cooperative department.

Since the cooperative department was established in 1955, a large number of cooperatives have emerged and are engaged in a variety of economic activities. These include consumer, agricultural, fishing, transport, livestock raising, groundnut marketing, dairy, artisanal, Gum Arabic, and credit cooperatives, in addition to numerous other secondary cooperatives at the local level (Cooperative Unions) that are overseen by an apex cooperative body.

The Co-operative Movement brings together about six million members throughout Sudan (Alowtaibi 2010). The number of cooperatives is 8988 included unions, the number of unions are 135 while institutions are 12 included the Military cooperative with the exception of the newly formulated cooperatives in Khartoum State.

-2-3:- Evolution of Cooperative Movement in the Sudan

In the mid of the 1920s, the commercial cotton farming started in the Gezira scheme, coincident with construction of irrigation projects and passing of the Companies Law.

The consequent governments in Sudan were having different agenda and views regarding the cooperative movement. The British colonial and the native governments up to the end of the 1960s directed the cooperatives to be a means of wealth accumulation.

Following that, the government launched a financing program for these cooperatives ran by the Ministry of Finance, and then the program became, in 1959, a part of the Agricultural Bank of Sudan that aims to finance public, private and cooperatives. However, these sorts of finance have assisted to accumulate wealth in two ways. First to sustain the position of the elite groups including tribal, merchants and high rank officials who were the leaders of the agricultural cooperatives. The second is to free farmers with small ownership from the hard finance that was provided by the village merchants, which is locally known as shail or the crop mortgage. It is essentially a system of crop mortgage under which the borrower sells in advance a certain part of the future crop in exchange for a loan from a village trader, a landlord, a relative or a friend; sufficient knowledge about the borrower is a prerequisite, and hence there is no collateral. Informal loans may be in cash or in kind, but repayment is usually made in kind at lender-set prices that are significantly lower than harvest prices (FAO, 2005).

In the 1970s, under May Revolution (Numeri regime), the cooperative legislation of 1948 was changed for the first time. The cooperative membership was opened with a minimum limit of 50 persons, and cooperatives were allowed for some privileges including tax exemption. The cooperative movement became a part of the political system of the regime, with a wide organizational structure.

In the 1989, regime, cooperatives were legalized to work. Many of them were under the hands of the supporters of the ruling party, who tend to neglect the general meeting and took serious decisions concerning the existence of cooperatives themselves. Some

cooperatives with valuable assets were privatized as they leased or sold to operate on the private basis.

In this context, the supportive economic and political external environment has its impacts on cooperatives, over years. But during the last three decades, since the 1980s, many economic changes were brought including structural adjustment programmes (SAPs), economic liberalization; technological changes that together form the phenomenon of globalization. Under this new environment, cooperatives started their challenges to cope with dramatic changes that form their relationship with the state across the world, in the developed and developing countries.

But with the application of the privatization policy in the 1990s, the cooperatives are largely marginalized, and their economic role is widely weakened under uncompetitive practices.

Nevertheless, Sudan has a long history in cooperative practices; historically there are some traditional practices forms of cooperation exist in different parts of the country across social and economic activities. These forms of traditional voluntary works provide a real base for the modern forms of cooperatives in the country. One may argue with Green (2002), these cooperatives have been developed in a local context to solve problems that beset ordinary people, based on the traditional mutual work in the specific local environment.

1- Types and Activities of cooperatives in the Sudan.

Cooperatives in Sudan are divided into five types: -

- Multipurpose cooperatives.
- Consumption cooperatives.
- Agriculture cooperatives.
- Professional cooperatives.
- Services cooperatives.

Most of the cooperatives are embarked in the above-mentioned areas of activities with an obvious concentration on the consumption type as it related with the provision of services to its members particularly the poor segment.

According to the cooperatives register the last number of the cooperatives is 8.988 associations in addition to the unions 135 union and 12 cooperatives institutions. Apart from these a few 169 associations which is stopped from work due to the loss of its assets. This is in addition to the newly formulated associations in Khartoum State which consist of 730 saving and credit cooperatives.

Chapter Three

Cooperatives and Equity support as Components of Self Employment: -

3.1. Introduction-

The so-called, "new world" of micro finance is not the first attempt to formalize the virtues of traditional methods of intermediation with a social rather than a business motive, Friedrich Raiffeisen started the first formal cooperative savings and credit organizations in Germany in 1848, and the first Indian Cooperative Credit Societies Act was passed in 1904.

These early and genuine groups came together to pool their funds and their expertise and facilitate intermediation between savers and borrowers beyond the local community.

Cooperatives and Credit unions have in some places continued both to grow and to serve the poor, and in many countries, and districts, they are the most important and successful financial institutions. Elsewhere however, and particularly in the poorer countries, cooperatives have been "hijacked" by the less poor, the landowners, and by allied political interests. Governments first became involved because of the need to protect very poor people from unscrupulous or incompetent promoters, but this very proper concern has often been corrupted by politicians, desire to protect and further their own interests.

Rural cooperatives have also traditionally served farmers, who own some land, however little. There are more and more people who live in rural areas but who own no land at all, at they are increasingly

earning their living from activities which have little or even nothing to do with agriculture. These people find it difficult to fit into the usual cooperative financial systems, since their patterns of financial needs and their assets are so different.

Traditional savings and credit mechanisms have thus existed all over the world for hundreds of years and have been the basis of important financial institutions of many different forms. Why then is there such world wide interest in micro finance, and what is different about the new micro finance institutions? Micro finance is in fact a very traditional and familiar form of business, which has evolved and indeed is still evolving in a variety of different ways to meet the needs of its many different customers, what, if anything, is new.

Some migrate to cities in search of employment, but government and public enterprises are down-sizing, and in spite of economic liberalization and restructuring private business, whether foreign or local, are not absorbing even a small proportion of the people who want jobs. As a result, the only option is some form of self-employment, whether in the countryside or in the town, and the so-called “informal sector:” or micro-enterprise, appears not to be a temporary waiting place for proper jobs, but a permanent and growing part of the economy (ibid).

3.2.1—Credits Cooperatives in Khartoum State:

Khartoum State is the pioneer State in the field of community development associations, Social Development Foundation (SDF) formulated 730 societies throughout the State with the purpose of organizing the community into local bodies these consider as an infrastructures for funding and credit provisioning for the ultra-poor and the economically active poor to prepare them to be credit worthy and hence to run their business. So, a huge number of lending and saving and Credit societies has been organized through all localities with a membership round 11000 member from women and men the

legal entity for these associations is the cooperative law as all of them has been registered under the cooperative law considering the fact that this is the only law which permit them to deal with lending and provisioning of financial services. it is worth mention here that the researcher had the honor to contribute on the formulation of these CBOs. These associations represent the bulk of community-based organizations as well as cooperatives associations their views were explored through the questionnaire designed for the purpose of this study.

3.3.1. Sudanese Development Association (SDA):

A group of women the majority of them were divorced, widowed, and displaced were enabled to establish three cooperatives that got permanent locations with the help of Oxfam working at that time and equipped them for their members in the main markets of the city. They are now working on a legal basis and are doing to set up a mutual fund for emergencies, needs of these isolated areas. The project started in 1986 and finalized in 1998 with creating 227 cooperatives working for 23,686 beneficiary families. The cooperatives operate to finance and marketing the groundnuts product of the women members.

3-4.1. Agriculture Engineers Cooperative corporation:

This cooperative corporation established recently in Khartoum State to provide youth graduates of Agriculture faculties in Sudan based in Khartoum it began its work by providing supporting services for the agriculture engineers in their field. The membership of this corporation is 1999 member the majority of them are university graduates and on the age group between 23- and above 30% are females while 70% are males.

-3.5-1.Cooperatives in the Red Sea State

Fishing cooperatives In the Red Sea area, operate in the country since the 1950s, they face financing constraints. Under the umbrella of the Graduates Employment Fund these cooperatives start to work provide employment opportunities the graduates.

3.6. 1. Cooperatives in South Kordofan State:-

3.7. 1- Elnuhud Cooperative Credit Project:-

This project was initiated in 1986; in Kordofan State (south-western Sudan following the famine strokes the area in 1984. The project aims to develop agriculture in the region, improve the income of small farmers, and meet the needs of these isolated areas. The project started in 1986 and finalized in 1998 with creating 227 cooperatives working for 23,686 beneficiary families. The cooperatives operate to finance and marketing the groundnuts product of the women members.

There are another type of cooperatives specialized on special issues such as Gum Arabic and other women productive associations which work as Revolving Funds under the supervision of IFAD.

3.8.1 -Sudia Association:--

It is a civil society organization focus on poverty reduction through community-based organization. This association working on group lending a group of more than fifty women organized in a cooperative form and applies for the agriculture loan from Sudia.

3.9.1 -Small Enterprises Chamber North Kordofan:-

This chamber is a local chamber working in coordination with the federal one. It comprised of 27 units of different specializations. Some of these units were registered under cooperative law.

3.9.2. The Aspects of unemployment in The Sudan

This section deals with reviewing the extent of the unemployment in the Sudan and its effects in the formal and informal sectors bearing in mind the increasing rate of the graduates and the education revolution which the country embarked on it since December 1989, and the spread of poverty in the country particularly in Khartoum State the capital.

According to the 1993 census, the population of the Sudan was found to be approximately 30 million 49.80% are women. The

economic growth of the country has been considerably fluctuating compared to annual population growth of 2.9%. The level of poverty has steadily increased, poverty is reflected in the various economic indicators as unemployment is one of the most closely watched indicators for economic health, along with gross domestic product (GDP). The unemployment rate has an inverse relationship with the stock market and inflation, two key metrics for the overall economy.

The informal sector absorbed the bulk of the labor force of both sexes particularly in the urban areas where the migrants and displaced concentrated. The informal sector characterized by easy access and a variety of job opportunities which needs no high skills such as food making and services. These figures generally reflect the reality of women status and their share in development and indicate the importance of narrowing this gap if we want women empowerment and widening employment opportunities and other benefits.

The unemployment rate in the Sudan increased by 3.2 percentage points (18.19 percent) since 2022. The unemployment rate thereby reached its highest value in the observed period.

Although unemployment among graduates remains high, some unemployed graduates have decided to look for alternative means of income to sustain their families. They do this even though only white-collar jobs are valued in the Sudan. They formulated associations at the grassroots under the umbrella of the Social Development Foundations (SDF) so as to receive microfinance from the Banks or the NGOs.

Youth unemployment in the Sudan remains a global threat to the achievement of the United Nations' sustainable development goals, particularly in the Sudan. It makes it more difficult to combat unemployment in all of its manifestations, restricts chances to advance inclusive and sustainable economic growth, and makes it

more difficult for a nation to lessen inequality. The unemployment rate is particularly high among graduates, because the environment is prone to volatility caused by poor governance, chronic conflicts, and corruption. Unemployed graduates who lack effective strategies risk failing to generate income for themselves and their families. So, they formulated community associations in different forms cooperatives could be one of these forms.

A broad range of cooperatives, including workers cooperatives, in rural, urban, areas have existed in the Sudan. And can assist in job creation through self-help entrepreneurship. The role of cooperatives in microfinance as enhancing job creation had also existed.

3.9.3. Credits Cooperatives in Khartoum State the Case study:-

-Khartoum State is the capital of Sudan it represents all Sudanese tribes due to the shift of the population from the States to the capital for different reasons conflicts, drought, and war. As stated, before the bulk of population are in Khartoum due to the previous reasons.

Number of Member in Cooperatives

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	2.0	2.0	2.0
	50	3	6.0	6.1	8.2
	59	1	2.0	2.0	10.2
	65	1	2.0	2.0	12.2
	70	1	2.0	2.0	14.3
	80	1	2.0	2.0	16.3
	81	1	2.0	2.0	18.4
	90	2	4.0	4.1	22.4
	95	1	2.0	2.0	24.5
	98	1	2.0	2.0	26.5
	100	6	12.0	12.2	38.8
	102	1	2.0	2.0	40.8
	110	2	4.0	4.1	44.9
	120	1	2.0	2.0	46.9
	135	1	2.0	2.0	49.0
	150	6	12.0	12.2	61.2
	153	1	2.0	2.0	63.3
	170	1	2.0	2.0	65.3
	185	1	2.0	2.0	67.3
	200	2	4.0	4.1	71.4
	210	1	2.0	2.0	73.5
	235	1	2.0	2.0	75.5
	250	5	10.0	10.2	85.7
	300	1	2.0	2.0	87.8
	350	1	2.0	2.0	89.8
	450	2	4.0	4.1	93.9
	460	1	2.0	2.0	95.9
	560	1	2.0	2.0	98.0
	650	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	49	98.0	100.0	
Missing	System	1	2.0		
Total		50	100.0		

The above table shows the number of cooperatives sample in Khartoum whose filled the questionnaire.

Source: Researcher own data.

Table No (1)

		State			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Khartoum	50	100.0	100.0	100.0

The above table indicates the assessment of cooperatives sample location based 100% of them based in Khartoum.

Source: Researcher own data.

Table No (2) Indicates the social status of cooperatives samples.

		Social status			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	3	6.0	8.6	8.6
	Job	16	32.0	45.7	54.3
	Jobless	16	32.0	45.7	100.0
	Total	35	70.0	100.0	
Missing	System	15	30.0		
Total		50	100.0		

Source: Researcher own data.

Do Cooperatives play an important role in the Socio - economic of the state where you are located ?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	50	100.0	100.0	100.0

The above table indicates the socioeconomic role played by the cooperatives by 100%.

Table No (3)

What progress has been made in the Coop. Sector in your State till date?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulati Percen
Valid	35	70.0	70.0	7
access to finance	1	2.0	2.0	7
community development	1	2.0	2.0	7
external expose	1	2.0	2.0	7
health insurance	1	2.0	2.0	7
illiteracy training	1	2.0	2.0	8
improving infrastructure	1	2.0	2.0	8
improving socioeconomic conditions	1	2.0	2.0	8
increasing the membership	1	2.0	2.0	8
job creation	1	2.0	2.0	8
make availbe housing finance	1	2.0	2.0	9
microfinance	1	2.0	2.0	9
no progress	1	2.0	2.0	9
training	1	2.0	2.0	9
training and gapacity building	1	2.0	2.0	9
women development	1	2.0	2.0	10
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates the progress made by cooperatives in financial services, as 70% provide financial services 72% provide community development services,74% provide external opportunities for marketing,8.0 % provide health insurance services,80% provide illiteracy education,84% said that it provided them with jobs opportunities, make available housing finance by 90%, access to microfinance by 92%.Those who said there is No progress are 9%, training and capacity building 98%,women development comprised 98%.

Source: Researcher own data.

Table No (4)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Agriculture

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	14	28.0	28.0	28.0
no	36	72.0	72.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that 28% of the cooperatives is working in the agriculture.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (5)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Fisheries

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	2	4.0	4.0	4.0
no	48	96.0	96.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that 4.0% of cooperatives working in fisheries.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Fisheries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	2	4.0	4.0	4.0
	No	48	96.0	96.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (6)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Finance/Banking

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	31	62.0	62.0	62.0
	no	19	38.0	38.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that 62% of cooperatives providing Microfinance.
Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (7)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Consumer/ retail

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	33	66.0	66.0	66.0
no	17	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that 66% percentage of cooperatives working in consumer retail.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (8)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Health

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	17	34.0	34.0	34.0
no	33	66.0	66.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that 34% of cooperatives providing health insurance to their members.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (9)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Manufacturing

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	35	70.0	70.0	70.0
no	15	30.0	30.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 70% of cooperatives working in manufacturing in food processing.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (10)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Housing

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	2	4.0	4.0	4.0
no	48	96.0	96.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates that 4.0% of cooperatives providing access to housing finance.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (11)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Insurance

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	4	8.0	8.0	8.0
no	46	92.0	92.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table indicates 8.0% of cooperatives active in insurance.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (12)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Tourism

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	2	4.0	4.0	4.0
no	48	96.0	96.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 4.0%. of cooperatives working in the tourism.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (13)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - Workers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	6	12.0	12.0	12.0
no	44	88.0	88.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 12.0% of cooperatives are in services Sector.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (14)

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active - others

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	4	8.0	8.0	8.0
no	46	92.0	92.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 8.0%. of cooperatives working in other activities.

Source: Researcher own data.

Specify the economic sectors where your cooperatives are most active -

Table No (15)

Cooperatives promote socio economic development

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid high priority	37	74.0	77.1	77.1
medium priority	3	6.0	6.3	83.3
low priority	8	16.0	16.7	100.0
Total	48	96.0	100.0	
Missing System	2	4.0		
Total	50	100.0		

The above table shows that 77.1% of cooperatives promote socioeconomic development.

Source: Researcher own data.

Cooperatives promote socio economic development

Table (16)

Cooperatives help generate employment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	high priority	26	52.0	54.2	54.2
	medium priority	7	14.0	14.6	68.8
	low priority	14	28.0	29.2	97.9
	Total	48	96.0	100.0	100.0
Missing	System	2	4.0		
Total		50	100.0		

The above table shows that 54.2 % of cooperatives help generating employment opportunities.

Source: Researcher own data.

Table No (17)

Specify the major challenges do cooperatives face

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	35	70.0	70.0	70.0
Access to capital	1	2.0	2.0	72.0
Collateral	1	2.0	2.0	74.0
collateral	1	2.0	2.0	76.0
Default	1	2.0	2.0	78.0
Exposure to arrest	1	2.0	2.0	80.0
Finance	1	2.0	2.0	82.0
Grace period	1	2.0	2.0	84.0
in accessibility to finance	1	2.0	2.0	86.0
Legislations and Procedures	1	2.0	2.0	88.0
Marketing	2	4.0	4.0	92.0
No institutional	1	2.0	2.0	94.0
Training	2	4.0	4.0	98.0
Sustainability	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher own data.

Table No (18)

**Do you think there is a need for a global effort to promote cooperative
and raise awareness on the role of cooperatives in socio - economic
development**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	50	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher own data.

Chapter Four

Summary, Results and Recommendations.

4.1. Summary: -

The issue of unemployment among youth has gained a considerable attention over the globe young people (population ages between 15 and 24) have fewer opportunities to participate in labor markets compared to the active adult population. Recent statistics shows that young people in the world are estimated to be about 1.8 billion, representing one quarter of the world's population (Population Reference Bureau, 2013). More than 70 million of them are unemployed with drastic economic and social conditions. In addition, most of employed youth workers engage in hazardous jobs and informal sector, and their transition to decent work is slow and difficult (ILO, 2013).

Sudan has witnessed development crises, internal conflicts, ethnic strife, war and socio-political and economic disasters that collaboratively impede transparency and equity in the allocation of national resources. As regards human

resources development, it is worth mentioning that the impact of macro-economic policies in human development has both negative and positive bearings on human resources development agenda and infrastructure. The existence of unemployment pockets differs from one State to the other, and directly affects both rural communities and urban centers. So, it is argued that it is the planning and recruitment policies and procedures that are responsible from unemployment among the youth in the formal sector.

The recent statistics of International Labour Organization (ILO) indicates that youth unemployment in Sudan accounting for about 24.5% in 2013, which is higher than the average rate of African countries and the Arab Region.

The findings of the questionnaire conducted for the purposes of this study show that 54.2 % cooperatives help generating employment opportunities. This reflects that the majority of unemployed youth respondents prefer self-employment. The findings of the questionnaire indicates that 62% of cooperatives providing Microfinance.

4.2- Results: -

The study reveals the following results: -

- 1) In the Sudan access to credit allows poor people to take the advantage of economic opportunities. While increased earnings are by no means automatic. It is evident that clients who join a cooperative and obtain micro credits have better economic conditions and have also shown that over a long period of time many clients do come out of unemployment

By reducing vulnerability and increasing earnings, members can afford their living expenses. This fact is ascertain by the result of the questionnaire conducted for the purpose of this study 54.2 % of cooperatives help generating employment opportunities. And shows that 12.0% of cooperatives are in services sector. 58.3 % of cooperatives help ensure food security. that 81.3 % of cooperatives help in reducing poverty. that 75.0% of cooperatives promote rural small enterprises. 77.1% of cooperatives promote socioeconomic development.

4:3- **Recommendations**

Relying on the above the following recommendations could be suggested: -

4.3.1. In the area of Youth Employment: -

- Matching between the education outcome and the labor market demand should be considered.
- Reenforce and enhance the various initiatives pertaining to youth employment to reduce unemployment among both sexes.
- Work in the informal sector should be recognized as active work which constitutes to development.
- Young people should be provided with formal and informal training and professional training to enhance their access to employment and thereby improve their social well-being.

4.3.2. Recommendations in the area of cooperatives

The central recommendations in the area of cooperatives are as follows: -

In order to expand cooperatives sector and concept the study raise the following recommendations we need to adopt and emphasize cooperatives strategy that focuses on the following goals:-

- (5) Development of strategies that improve the sector based on the cooperatives values.
- (6) Development of specific policy to govern the sector and integrate it in the strategic plans of the country.
- (7) Mainstreaming cooperative culture and identification of the self-employment strategies that can take the youth into a level of socio- economic well being hence increase their autonomy.

- (8) Emphasis on capacity building management, business skills training and transparent, democratic structures are intended to ensure sound management and institutional sustainability.
- (9) Emphasis on capacity building management, business skills training and transparent, democratic structures are intended to ensure sound management and institutional sustainability.

Conclusion: -

To conclude we can ascertain the fact that cooperative model offers new opportunities to involve communities and individuals in socio -economic development process. And can facilitate smallholder farmers' youth and the needy segment in the society linkages to export markets and have the full potential to strengthen livelihood.

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